

BUILDING A SINGAPORE DIGITAL PRESERVATION COMMUNITY OF INTEREST TO FURTHER ADVOCACY AND ENGAGEMENT

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Abstract – The poster covers the National Library's role as custodian of Singapore's documentary heritage, with a focus on its efforts in being a leader in the field of digitisation and advocacy of digital preservation. Advocacy efforts include organising digital preservation talks and workshops to engage the community, and deepening collaboration between practitioners with the new Singapore community of interest.

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I. INTRODUCTION–DIGITAL PRESERVATION AND THE NATIONAL LIBRARY SINGAPORE

The National Library Singapore has been steadily digitising and preserving content as keepers under the “Singapore Storyteller” pillar [1] of the National Library Board's LAB25 (Library and Archives Blueprint 2025) with the objective of nurturing appreciation and understanding of Singapore's heritage through collecting, preserving, enabling use and discovery by connecting people to our content, and inspiring them to become next-generation creators. This objective aligns with the library's digital preservation policy which sets out our commitment to digitisation and digital preservation of the country's documentary heritage, and the long-term goal of being a leader on digital preservation in the region.

The poster highlights the library's efforts so far in advocating digital preservation and connecting with the people to fulfil the role as keeper of Singapore's heritage, and talks about the inaugural session of the new community of interest launching in May 2025.

II. LEADING, ADVOCATING, ENGAGING: EFFORTS MADE BY THE NATIONAL LIBRARY SINGAPORE

1. First a Practitioner, Then a Leader

In our efforts to become a thought leader in digital preservation, the national library provides staff with opportunities to further develop their skills with courses, seminars, conferences and self-directed learning, ensuring all relevant staff are appropriately skilled to carry out digital preservation activities. NLB joined the Digital Preservation Coalition (DPC) in 2021 to actively engage with the wider community and learn from other professional bodies. These efforts to stay ahead in the field has made NLB a good example for other local institutions to learn from.

2. Advocacy and Engagement Efforts

Concurrently, the National Library has been advocating digital preservation practices by engaging practitioners and the general public through talks since 2021. NL first collaborated with the DPC to promote awareness and understanding of digital preservation to the public with a workshop spread across five days from August to October 2021. The workshop covered different aspects of digital

preservation on each day and drew a total audience of nearly 400.

From 2021 to 2024, NL engaged the community through digital preservation talks, leveraging on invited DPC experts and digital preservation practitioners from different local organisations. Various topics and focus areas on digital preservation were covered across the eight sessions (e.g. *"The future of data storage for preservation"*, *"Digital preservation's importance to the community"*, *"Digital preservation skills for practitioners"*), amassing a total of over 1,000 participants over the 4 years.

Some participants have indicated the usefulness of these sessions and their desire for more in-depth and tailored coverage on how they can adopt digital preservation practices and toolkits for their own institution's use as digital preservation poses many challenges ranging from growing data volumes to the ever-increasing number of new file formats [2]. Taking inspiration from Weatherburn's paper [3], the National Library will spearhead a new Singapore community of interest amongst local tertiary libraries and heritage institutions.

III. DEEPENING COLLABORATION WITH THE NEW SINGAPORE COMMUNITY OF INTEREST

The objective of this new community of interest is to build a thriving local community conducted in-person that supports, encourages, and engages all members to actively pursue and ultimately reinvest their time in furthering digital preservation efforts in their organisations. Through sharing sessions with practitioners from multidisciplinary backgrounds, members of the community can deepen collaboration by networking and improving their practice with the provision of experience, resources and tools. The community also aims to provide an informal and welcoming platform for practitioners to provide mentorship to those less familiar with the field and encouraging newcomers or interested parties to join in and learn without being overwhelmed.

The inaugural session will take place in May 2025, and is fully in-person to promote engagement and establish stronger professional relationships. It opens with presentations from the National University of Singapore Libraries, Heritage Conservation Centre, and the National Library Board Singapore, followed by a moderated Q&A session to foster interaction.

IV. CONCLUSION

The National Library, as keeper and custodian of the country's documentary heritage, under the "Singapore Storyteller" pillar of the National Library Board's LAB25, has been digitising and preserving content in accordance with the library's digital preservation policy. With the long-term strategic goal of being a thought leader in the field of digital preservation, the National Library aims to ensure staff are adequately skilled in digital preservation practices to set an example for others to learn from. The National Library has also led numerous advocacy and engagement efforts since 2021, from conducting workshop sessions to organising talks with invited subject experts and will continue to do so. On top of that, the National Library plans to ramp up engagement by starting a Singapore community of interest for digital preservation to create an informal platform for practitioners to deepen collaboration and mutual learning. The community aims to promote sharing of experience, resources and tools, and foster networking and building of professional relationships to further the advocacy and importance of digital preservation among heritage institutions.

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